
POSSIBILITIES OF THE LISTENING METHOD IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the process of learning a foreign language by listening, methods of repeated listening, in particular, the formation of listening skills, improving pronunciation by listening. The importance of interactive methods that develop listening skills in teaching English is analyzed. In addition, the experience of a coach who developed his own system for us to speak English perfectly was given as an example.

Keywords. *listening, interactive, innovation, method, pronunciation, skill, audio, video, discipline.*

In today's age of advanced technologies, there seems to be no knowledge, skills and experience that humanity has not learned. In fact, new subjects that we want to learn are always being studied. We can know the results of research from the skills of scientists and doctors. Learning world languages means gaining experiences. Therefore, knowing the language is one of the important factors for the career. If we want to be successful at work and in life, we must start learning new languages. There are many ways, methods, tools ready for us to learn.

Considering the conditions of Uzbekistan, we have been teaching a foreign language, especially English, for many years in state and private preschools, general schools and universities. In addition, there are many language training centers. It is not about teaching the language, but how to teach it. In most cases, teenagers who leave school have a basic foundation, have memorized grammar, but have not developed listening and speaking skills, while reading and writing skills are very weak. Japanese-born teacher A.J.Hoge said: “One of the great problems in schools is that teachers have failed to recognize they must do more than lecture to and discipline their students. Truly great teachers are more than just lecturers, they are leaders and coaches who inspire their students to greatness. Studying grammar rules to speak

English is much like a soccer player studying physics to play soccer. It might be interesting (or not!), but it certainly will not help performance. Your job, therefore, is to stop “studying” English and start “playing” it!”[3].

In this article, we will analyze the method of the world-famous trainer to greatly improve listening and speaking skills. Who is he actually? A.J. Hoge is the founder and director of Effortless English LLC, and co-founder of Learn Real English and Business English Conversations. He has been described as “the world’s number one English teacher” and is famous as the host of The Effortless English Show, with over 41 million downloads worldwide. He has a master’s degree in TESOL and has been teaching English since 1996. A.J.Hoge teaches seminars around the world on the topics of English, public speaking, effective training methods, career development, and online marketing. [4]

When learning English, the more we listen to audio podcasts, watch videos in this language and do it every day, the most important thing is that if we listen again, our listening skills will improve and we will start speaking spontaneously. In this regard, the book "Effortless English: learn to speak like a native" by teacher A.J., which we are studying, is necessary and useful. The popular title by A.J.Hoge was written for the people in need for the most efficient and less time and effort consuming learning methods. This book is posted on the teacher's Telegram (https://t.me/A_j_hogee), You Tube (<https://youtube.com/c/AJHogeEffortlessEnglish>), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/ajhoge?t=AUVRW685v0TspDBEun9aUQ&s=35>), Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/ajhogeclub/?ref=share>) social network pages and website (<https://www.ajhogeclub.com/>) in audio and video format with his voice and detailed information. They can be heard over and over again every day and it is not boring at all.

The book by A.J. Hoge, one of the leading and recognized experts, released it to teach readers the most effective methods for learning to speak this language fluently and with enough confidence. The book will tell you how to speak without any nervousness and shyness, experiencing no fear at all, how to achieve high scores when passing IELTS and TOEFL tests, how to build up the vocabulary in a short period of time; you will also feel much stronger and calmer when speaking English, if you follow all recommendations provided by the author. The book has been specifically designed and released for the people who have already been studying English for years but still don't speak well. The materials in the book are very

interesting and authentic - they are not too difficult to use. It is really worth reading and is full of truly wonderful tips. Huge amount of useful information will help you learn English language effectively. You will see how fast your knowledge of English will be improving once you have started using this book every day. Your vocabulary will grow up, and grammar skills will improve, it will be much easier for you to communicate the other people, write letters, read texts and understand them properly. [5]

How you learn faster and avoid embarrassing mistakes when you download the course:

- The incredible way you “Learn Grammar Without “Rules”: Use English grammar correctly by learning grammar in a natural way.
- The Deep Learning method that helps you use English faster. Remember English words and grammar– and use them in real conversations. Feel strong about your speaking ability.
- The way you learn English in a relaxing way by listening to real English articles about interesting topics. Imagine thinking, smiling, and laughing while learning.
- The way you avoid stress and slow speech. The fun and crazy mini-stories train you to speak and respond faster.
- How the best English speakers learn, how they study,- and how you can use the methods they use. To be successful, copy the most successful people.
- Lessons that help you learn English without boredom- no more textbooks, no more tests, no more “exercises”.
- How you meet other English speakers and talk with them. Meet other friendly Power English members just like you. [6]

THE CONTENTS OF THE BOOK:

Chapter 1: A better way to learn English

Chapter 2: The problem with schools

Chapter 3: Psychology is more important than grammar and vocabulary

Chapter 4: Your beliefs determine your English success

Chapter 5: English is a physical sport

Chapter 6: Use big real world goals to motivate yourself for success

Chapter 7: Program your brain for English success

Chapter 8: Babies learn best The Effortless English™ engine

Chapter 9: The first rule – learn phrases not words

- Chapter 10: The second rule: grammar study kills your English speaking
Chapter 11: The third rule: learn with your ears, not with your eyes
Chapter 12: The fourth rule – repetition is the key to spoken mastery
Chapter 13: The fifth rule: learn grammar intuitively and unconsciously
Chapter 14: The sixth rule: learn real English and trash your textbooks
Chapter 15: The seventh rule: learn English with compelling stories
Chapter 16: Your daily English learning plan
Chapter 17: The power of pleasure reading
Chapter 18: The secret to good English writing
Chapter 19: Why you should not practice speaking
Chapter 20: English is the language of international business
Chapter 21: How to give powerful English presentations
Chapter 22: English connects you with the world
Chapter 23: The effortless English code and mission. [4]

In conclusion, it can be said that it is useful to use such methods in learning not only English, but also other foreign languages. For this, first of all, there must be three things: aspiration, interest and desire. Today, there are many people who, like A.J., are running their own blogs on social media to teach languages. A.J. Hoge’s listening method also develops speaking skills. When we hear words and sentences over and over again, we begin to repeat them automatically. A.J. Hoge’s purpose is to quickly pronounce words that are stuck in our brains. As we begin to listen and understand, our reading skills improve, and the more we read, the faster our writing skills. In the book, we can see his teaching lessons from school problems to human psychology and self-confidence. He also says that grammar kills a person’s ability to speak, that it is necessary to write down phrases rather than just memorizing words, that language should be learned by ear rather than by eye. He even recommends listening at any time of the day, on the street, at home, at work, studying or doing housework. In his book, he shares not only the process of listening and speaking, but also the secrets of writing and reading skills. Therefore, English or any other foreign language is a facility that connects us with the world, and learning it is not as difficult as we think.

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